

Studies in Sulphonamides : Part III. Condensation of 2-acetamido 6-naphthalene Sulphonyl Chloride with Ammonia and Twentynine different Primary Aromatic Amines and Biological Evaluation of the Sulphonamides

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2-Acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride was condensed with ammonia and twentynine different primary aromatic amines in presence of either dry pyridine or a mixture of dry pyridine and acetone; hydrolysis of the resulting acetamido compounds furnished the corresponding N⁶-substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides.

These compounds were screened for their antibacterial properties and it was observed that while some of the N¹-substituted 4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamides were active against *S. Aureus* and *E. coli*, none of the N⁶-substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides possessed any activity. These findings indicate that the position of the groups in the naphthalene ring bears a relationship with the activity of these compounds.

Several aminonaphthalene sulphonamides were synthesised and tested¹ for their antibacterial and antiviral activities and it was reported that the antibacterial properties of these were less marked than those of sulphanilamide and its derivatives. Later synthesis² and antiviral effects of N¹-substituted 4-acetamido 1-naphthalene and 4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamides were studied and it was observed that some of these derivatives were found active against Encephalitis Japonica *in vitro*. The most active compound against neutropic Japanese encephalitis virus reported³ was N¹-dodecanoyl 4-acetamido 1-naphthalene sulphonamide. 4-Acylamino 1-naphthalene and N¹-dodecanoyl 4-acetylamino 1-naphthalene sulphonamides were also synthesised to test their antiviral activity.

The synthesis of N¹-acyl 4-aminonaphthalene sulphonamides and the N¹-acylation of 4-acetylamino 1-naphthalene sulphonamide has also been reported⁴. Preparation of some salts of acetaminonaphthalene sulphonic acid lauroylamide, synthesis of 4-hydroxy 1-naphthalene sulphoacylamide and 1-(aminoacyl-amino) naphthalene 4-sulpholauroylamide has also been reported⁵ and these compounds showed virus inhibitory effect.

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In continuation of our work^{6,7} and in view of the encouraging results obtained during the study on the synthesis of some 4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamides and their anti-bacterial properties, the work has been extended to the preparation and screening of several N⁶-substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides. Equimolecular quantities of 2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride and different primary aromatic amino compounds were condensed either in presence of dry pyridine or dry pyridine—acetone mixture. The acid chloride was prepared by heating 2-acetonaphthylamine with chlorosulphonic acid in the molar ratio of 5 : 1 at room temperature; these reactions were exothermic and in some cases the base readily dissolved in the sulphonyl chloride and on keeping deposited the amide while in others the reaction was instantaneous and the acetamido product separated out. The yields were, however, improved by using an extra molecule of the base and the acetamido products (Table I) separated out mostly at room temperature; these were crystallised either from absolute or dilute ethanol. Hydrolysis of these was accomplished by refluxing with dilute hydrochloric acid to give the corresponding N⁶-substituted 2-aminonaphthalene 6-sulphonamides (Table II) whereas N¹-substituted 4-acetamido 1-naphthalene sulphonamides were deacetylated by refluxing with aqueous sodium hydroxide^{6,7,8} for several hours.

These compounds were later screened for their antibacterial properties *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Our studies revealed that whereas N¹-substituted 4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamides were active, their isomeric N⁶-substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides were devoid of activity thereby indicating the effect of the positions of the groups in the naphthalene ring. This finding is in agreement with the earlier studies of sulphanilamide, orthanilamide and metanilamide where the last two were found to be inactive.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride : 2-Aceto-naphthalide (50 g; 0.02 mol) was added gradually under stirring to chlorosulphonic acid (155 g; 1.33 mol) cooled to 0° (ice); after the addition was complete, the mixture was stirred vigorously for further 2 hr. at room temperature. The dark grayish syrupy liquid was slowly poured over crushed ice and the solid sulphonyl chloride separated out which was filtered under suction.

Pure *2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride* was crystallised from anhydrous benzene as a pinkish white granular solid which softened at 179–80° but did not melt even upto 290°. (Yield : 52.5 g; 67.8%). (Found : C, 50.5; H, 3.7; S, 11.1. C₁₂H₁₀O₃ NSCl requires C, 50.8; H, 3.5; S, 11.3%).

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TABLE I

Comp. No.	R'	Reaction Temp. °C	Time for the Reaction hr.	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mole. formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
								Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1	H	30—40	½	Brownish-red crystals	245—6	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	54.4	54.5	4.5	4.5
2	Phenyl	Room Temp.	½	Pinkish-white crystals	214	59.9	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	63.3	63.5	4.6	4.7
3	2'-Chlorophenyl	"	1	Light-brown crystals	203—4	51.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SCl	57.5	57.6	3.9	4.0
4	3'- "	Ice-bath	½	White crystals	206	55.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SCl	57.6	57.6	3.8	4.0
5	4'- "	Room Temp.	½	Greyish white crystals	225	59.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SCl	57.7	57.6	3.9	4.0
6	2'-Bromophenyl	"	½	White crystals	256	41.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SBr	51.6	51.5	3.4	3.5
7	3'- "	"	½	" "	200	35.6	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SBr	51.4	51.5	3.6	3.5
8	4'- "	Ice-bath	2	Light-brown crystals	230—1	53.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SBr	51.7	51.5	3.8	3.5
9	2'-Iodo-phenyl	30—40	2	White crystals	215	42.6	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SI	46.0	46.3	2.8	2.9
10	3'- "	"	2	White crystals	268	46.9	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SI	46.1	46.3	2.9	2.9
11	4'- "	"	2	Dark-grey crystals	195—6	36.2	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ SI	46.3	46.3	2.9	2.9
12	2'-Nitrophenyl	"	2	Yellowish-brown crystals	300(d.)	41.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	56.0	56.1	3.7	3.6
13	3'- "	60—75	5	Light-brown crystals	300(d.)	36.1	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	56.0	56.1	3.7	3.6
14	4'- "	70—5	6	" "	Did not melt upto 300	33.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	55.9	56.1	3.4	3.6
15	2'-Methylphenyl	Room Temp.	1	Pinkish-white crystals	209—10	41.1	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	64.2	64.4	5.1	5.0

*N*⁶-Substituted 2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonamides (R = —COCH₃)R'.HNSO₂

TABLE-I—CONTD

Comp. No.	R'	Reaction Temp. °C	Time for the Reaction hr.	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mole. formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
								Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
16	3'-Methoxyphenyl	Room Temp	1	Pinkish-white crystals	200	48.9	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	64.3	64.4	4.9	5.0
17	4' "	"	2	White crystals	240	58.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	64.4	64.4	5.1	5.0
18	2'-Methoxyphenyl	"	1	"	217	46.8	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	61.7	61.6	4.6	4.8
19	3' "	"	1	"	256	49.5	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	61.6	61.6	4.7	4.8
20	4' "	"	2	Light violet crystals	224-5	46.8	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	61.8	61.6	4.6	4.8
21	2'-Ethoxyphenyl	35-45	1	Greyish-white crystals	230	41.6	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S	62.4	62.5	5.1	5.2
22	3' "	80	4	White crystals	249-50	38.2	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S	62.3	62.5	5.2	5.2
23	4' "	45	2	"	290	56.4	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S	62.2	62.5	5.0	5.2
24	4'-Chloro-2'-methoxyphenyl	45-50	4	Violet crystals	250(d.)	49.7	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ SCl	58.7	58.6	4.2	4.3
25	5' "	"	2	Greyish white crystals	256(d.)	60.0	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ SCl	58.5	58.6	4.3	4.3
26	5'-Nitro-2'-methylxyphenyl.	45	4	Yellowish-brown crystals	300(d.)	29.9	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₃ S	57.0	57.1	4.2	4.2
27	5'-Chloro-2'-methoxyphenyl.	Room Temp.	2	Dark brown crystals	265	41.8	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ SCl	56.2	56.3	4.1	4.2
28	4'-Nitro-2'-methoxyphenyl.	100	4	Brown crystals	275-6	57.5	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₃ S	54.8	54.9	4.0	4.1
29	5'-Nitro-2'-methoxyphenyl.	45	2	-do-	274-5	28.7	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₃ S	54.9	54.9	4.0	4.1
30	4'-Methoxy-2'-nitrophenyl.	80	2	Dark brown crystals	300(d.)	28.7	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₃ S	54.8	54.9	4.2	4.1

TABLE II
*N*⁶-Substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides (R = H).

Comp. No.	Mol. Formula	Solvent	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %	Carbon %		Hydrogen %		Sulphur %	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	Abs. ethanol	Pinkish-white granules	234	71.4	54.2	54.0	4.8	4.8	14.1	14.4
2.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	Ethanol	White crystals	226	68.4	64.2	64.4	4.4	4.7	10.5	10.7
3.	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ SCl	"	White crystals	225	61.9	57.4	57.7	4.2	3.9	9.3	9.6
4.	"	"	Pinkish-white needles	216	67.5	57.3	57.7	4.1	3.9	9.4	9.6
5.	"	"	Colourless needles	213-4	72.0	57.9	57.7	3.7	3.9	9.8	9.6
6.	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ SBr	"	White crystals	280	66.6	50.6	50.9	3.2	3.4	8.2	8.5
7.	"	Abs. alcohol	White leaflets	200	66.6	50.7	50.9	3.7	3.4	8.3	8.5
8.	"	"	Light brown needles	235	70.0	50.6	50.9	3.4	3.4	8.7	8.5
9.	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ SI	Ethanol	White crystals	167	39.7	45.5	45.2	3.3	3.0	7.4	7.5
10.	"	Abs. alcohol	" "	260	54.9	45.6	45.2	3.2	3.0	7.7	7.5
11.	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ SI	"	Greyish-white crystals	216	52.7	45.4	45.2	3.4	3.0	7.1	7.5
12.	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ S	"	Grey-crystals	300(d.)	50.5	55.7	55.9	3.5	3.8	9.6	9.3
13.	"	Ethanol	Dark-brown needles	300(d.)	50.5	55.8	55.9	3.6	3.8	9.5	9.3
14.	"	Abs. alcohol	Greyish-white crystals	241-2	45.4	56.2	55.9	3.7	3.8	9.1	9.3
15.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	"	White leaflets	215	70.8	65.5	65.3	5.3	5.1	9.9	10.2

TABLE II—Contd.

Comp. No.	Mol. formula	Solvent	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %	Carbon %		Hydrogen %		Sulphur %	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
16.	$C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2S$	Ethanol	White crystals	195-6	79.4	65.6	65.3	5.4	5.1	10.4	10.2
17.	"	"	Pinkish-white crystals	228-9	85.0	65.1	65.3	5.3	5.1	10.5	10.2
18.	$C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2S$	Abs. alcohol	White crystals	232	78.9	62.4	62.1	4.6	4.8	9.4	9.7
19.	"	Ethanol	Colourless prisms	246-7	56.4	62.3	62.1	4.5	4.8	9.5	9.7
20.	"	"	Pinkish-white needles	230	64.8	62.5	62.1	4.6	4.8	9.9	9.7
21.	$C_{18}H_{18}O_3N_2S$	Abs. alcohol	White crystals	261-2	41.7	63.4	63.1	5.5	5.2	9.1	9.3
22.	"	Ethanol	"	275	37.4	63.3	63.1	5.4	5.2	9.5	9.3
23.	$C_{18}H_{18}O_3N_2S$	"	Pinkish white crystals	236	73.6	63.2	63.1	5.0	5.2	9.6	9.3
24.	$C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_2S$	Abs. alcohol	Light grey crystals	300(d.)	64.4	59.1	58.8	4.5	4.3	9.5	9.2
25.	"	"	Light grey crystals	300(d.)	70.0	58.6	58.8	4.6	4.3	9.4	9.2
26.	$C_{17}H_{15}O_4N_3S$	"	Brown needles	265	33.5	57.3	57.1	4.3	4.1	8.7	8.9
27.	$C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_2S$	"	Light-brown crystals	200-1	50.2	56.4	56.2	4.3	4.1	8.5	8.8
28.	$C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_3S$	"	Light-yellow crystals	241	63.0	54.6	54.8	4.2	4.0	8.8	8.6
29.	"	"	Brown crystals	300(d.)	33.1	54.5	54.8	4.4	4.0	8.3	8.6
30.	"	Ethanol	Dark-brown crystals	300(d.)	30.9	54.6	54.8	4.3	4.0	8.4	8.6

(d.) denotes decomposition.

*N*⁶-substituted 2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonamides were prepared by adding 2-acetamido 6-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride (1 mol) to the base (1 mol) in acetone, containing traces of pyridine and stirring vigorously for 2 to 3 hrs. The reaction product was poured into water containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml for every 100 ml of water) and the precipitated product filtered at the suction, washed, dried and crystallised.

*N*⁶-substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides were obtained by refluxing the above acetamido products, either with aqueous sodium hydroxide or dilute hydrochloric acid. The products were filtered under suction, washed with cold water and pure *N*⁶-substituted 2-amino 6-naphthalene sulphonamides were crystallised from absolute ethanol.

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